

MultiXscale

Report on support for emerging system architectures

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	Contributors:	Bob Dröge (RIJKSUNIGRON), Kenneth Hoste (UGent), Lara Peeters (UGent), Caspar van Leeuwen (SURF), Satish Kamath (SURF), Alan O'Cais (UB), Richard Topouchian (UiB), Thomas Röblitz (UiB), Julián Morillo (BSC)
	Reviewed by:	Thomas Röblitz (UiB), Kenneth Hoste (UGent)
	Approved by:	Alan Ó Cais (UB)

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¹p.m.santos.neves@rug.nl

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Executive Summary

In this report, we summarize the process for supporting new CPU microarchitectures and GPUs in the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) software stack within the MultiXscale Centre of Excellence. The main purpose of EESSI is to provide optimized software applications seamlessly to users while supporting the widest possible range of systems, from laptops to the largest exascale High Performance Computing (HPC) clusters such as the JUPITER system. Consequently, keeping up with new and emerging system architectures is critical to ensure new systems also have access to the optimized software stack. This work ensures that emerging system architectures are available through EESSI's continuous deployment, and thus, that an increasing number of users can benefit from optimized software installations. We describe the progress regarding the support for accelerators, in particular NVIDIA and AMD GPUs.

The support for GPUs was substantially improved, and the number of available build environments increased. The effort to expand the software stack with a large matrix of CPU architectures and GPU combinations is high, but its expansion is well underway. Thanks to the access of numerous European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC) sites, Tier-1 and Tier-2 sites across Europe, and the previously used Microsoft Azure and Amazon AWS cloud platforms, we are diversifying our build infrastructure, which gives us access to critical CPU and GPU combinations and allows us to spread the computational effort among different systems and providers.

Besides the gradual increase of the total number of available software packages since the official release of the first EESSI version (2023.06 in late 2023), 7 new CPU microarchitectures are supported, raising the count of the initially supported architectures from 6 to 13. These include both `x86_64` and `arch64` CPU families, such as AMD Zen 4 and NVIDIA Grace.

The separate `riscv.eessi.io` software stack has also vastly grown, consisting now of a much larger number of RISC-V compatible applications. The method to build it has also been brought closer to the general software building workflow for `software.eessi.io`, which is a major milestone towards integrating the "experimental" RISC-V software stack into the production version served via `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io`.

We also detail the process of adding new CPU targets and accelerators to the existing software stack and how the decision of such additions is taken. By having clear processes and documentation EESSI can keep growing sustainably while meeting the already high expectations of the user community.

Finally, the development repository `dev.eessi.io` is available to MultiXscale CoE researchers, allowing them to build, test, and deploy their software to EuroHPC sites and beyond in a quick and flexible way. We expect this to speed up development cycles, enable testing and Continuous Integration (CI) on actual hardware to increase software quality; all of which are desirable aspects of modern software development.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable concerns the results achieved in Task 1.2. We describe the progress, milestones, and ongoing work in supporting optimized software builds for emerging CPU architectures in EESSI. In addition, we discuss lessons learned while developing our procedure to add additional CPU targets to existing EESSI versions, which was done repeatedly for the first production version of EESSI – 2023.06.

We detail the status and ongoing development of the ARM software stack which now includes the addition of NVIDIA Grace to the existing `generic`, Neoverse N1, Neoverse V1 targets and we provide an outline to enable support for Fujitsu A64FX. Regarding the `x64_86` CPU microarchitectures, we describe the inclusion and parity of builds for AMD Genoa (`zen4`) in EESSI as well as Intel Sapphire Rapids.

Similarly, we describe our work to support AMD accelerators and ROCm. Lastly, we describe the ongoing work developing the RISC-V software stack in the dedicated CernVM File System (`CernVM-FS`) repository `riscv.eessi.io`.

1.2 Target audience

This deliverable is aimed at HPC system administrators, users and researchers interested in software builds optimized for specific CPU microarchitectures and accelerators (GPUs). While primarily aiming for using EESSI on HPC systems, researchers and users at large who are interested in maximizing the performance of their scientific software will also benefit from the advances described in this report.

1.3 Deliverable outline

We cover the progress in supporting new CPU targets in Section 2 and include the criteria used to decide on the addition of new CPU microarchitectures.

In Section 3 we outline the improvements to the existing support for NVIDIA GPUs, and include a description of how the support for NVIDIA accelerator generations is integrated. In the same section, we also outline the important steps taken and progress achieved in supporting AMD ROCm and AMD GPUs.

We provide details on the current status of the RISC-V software stack in Section 4 and give an overview of the steps taken towards integrating it with `software.eessi.io`.

Lastly, in Section 5 we describe improvements to the support of emerging architectures such as a newly created workflow for quickly and robustly adding new CPU targets to the production software repository and on supporting developers in the MultiXscale CoE. Lastly, we introduce the development repository `dev.eessi.io` and describe how it can help the workflow of MultiXscale CoE developers.

1.4 Partner contributions

Partners in Task 1.2 (RIJKSUNI, BSC, UGent, SURE, UiB, UB) contributed as planned to the work described in this deliverable.

2 CPU targets

In this section, we elaborate on new CPU targets added to the EESSI software stack, which constitutes an update to the work already reported in Deliverable D1.1 "Report on shared software stack prototype" [1].

At the time of writing, the EESSI shared software stack provides optimized software for the following aarch64 CPU microarchitectures:

- Neoverse N1
- Neoverse V1
- NVIDIA Grace (Neoverse V2)
- Fujitsu A64FX (work in progress)

The supported x86_64 CPU microarchitectures:

- AMD Zen 2
- AMD Zen 3
- AMD Zen 4
- Intel Haswell
- Intel Skylake
- Intel Cascade Lake
- Intel Ice Lake

End-users with access to systems where the EESSI software repository `software.eessi.io` is available need only load the EESSI module and and key environment variables, e.g., `$MODULEPATH`, will be configured such that the best fitting / optimized installations are accessible via Lmod commands.

```
module use /cvmfs/software.eessi.io/init/modules
module load EESSI/2023.06
```

Software installations are located in subdirectories with standardised names (reflecting the output of `archspeg` and `archdetect`), for example, applications optimized for the ARM CPU microarchitecture Neoverse N1 are installed in the directory:

```
/cvmfs/software.EESSI.io/software/versions/2023.06/software/linux/aarch64/neoverse_n1/
```

Consequently, when new CPU targets are added to the software stack, a new subdirectory is created under `aarch64` or `x86_64` where appropriate. We detail the procedure for adding new CPU targets in Section 5.1.

For clients using a CPU that is not natively supported, the stack will fall back to one of the other targets that is fully compatible with the client's CPU. Ultimately, there is a `generic` fallback without microarchitecture-specific optimizations, but that will only be used for processors that have fewer CPU features than the oldest relevant.

2.1 Criteria for supporting new CPU targets

The current number of CPU microarchitectures used both in single user or HPC contexts is too large to cover comprehensively. More importantly, the differences in instruction sets between very similar CPU microarchitectures can be very small (for instance, Intel Haswell and Intel Broadwell are very similar). In such cases, the potential performance differences between both CPU microarchitectures are very small or even negligible. Furthermore, in order to natively compile optimized software, we need access to infrastructure providing the necessary hardware. Therefore, we focus only on building and delivering optimized software installations a subset of all existing CPU microarchitectures, while ensuring broad compatibility and optimized builds are available for the community.

We decide on which the relevant system architectures to be included directly in EESSI are by following a number of criteria:

- New system architectures that become available in EuroHPC systems, or that will be available in the near future;
- The addition of instructions that bring significant performance advantages and that are not available already in the instruction sets of the currently supported CPU targets;
- Ubiquity of given system architectures in national systems (Tier-1 and Tier-2 sites);

- Requests by the community for a particular system architecture for which there is a compelling case for inclusion. As an example, see the [request](#)² on the support portal for the inclusion of the Intel Sapphire Rapids software stack.
- Availability and access to hardware resources on which to build the corresponding software stack.

2.2 Emerging CPU targets

The NVIDIA Grace software stack has been added to `software.eessi.io` and it is now fully on par with other CPU targets, that is, it consists of over 1,000 software installations at the time of writing (end of June 2025), with more being added as part of the standard process of installing new software. NVIDIA Grace software was **not** built on the existing AWS and Azure cloud clusters. Software builds were possible due to the cooperation with the Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC) system administrators, who granted a few EESSI developers access to [JURECA](#)³, which is [equipped with some NVIDIA Grace hardware](#)⁴. The collaboration with JSC system administrators and user support managers has been beneficial for both parties - JSC and MultiXscale/EESSI - because users on JUPITER will get access to a broad range of software installations from early on, and it may be used on other systems equipped with this CPU microarchitecture.

The AMD Zen 4 and Intel Sapphire Rapids software stacks are on par with the already present CPU targets. This was done via the standard procedure using instances of the build-test-deploy bot running on Magic Castle clusters on Microsoft Azure and AWS. As part of the build process, a CI pipeline was devised to compare the new with existing software stacks, in order to validate that all software has been built and is available.

2.3 Other relevant CPU targets

While not an emerging architecture, as it was launched in 2019, building a Fujitsu A64FX software stack is of particular relevance for the EuroHPC system [Deucalion](#)⁵, since one of its main compute partitions is powered by this architecture. Software builds for A64FX were obtained through access to this system, and at the time of writing approximately 54% of the necessary software installations were ingested into the `software.eessi.io` CernVM-FS repository, amounting to a total of 525 installations at the time of writing. Due to the more limited availability of this architecture in cloud providers such as AWS and Microsoft Azure, the necessary instance of the build-test-deploy bot runs on the Deucalion system itself, for which Minho Advanced Computing Center (MACC) system administrators kindly provided us access via a service account. In all other aspects the build process is identical to that of building for other CPU targets.

Support for Intel Cascade Lake and Ice Lake has been added recently and their software substacks are now fully on par with those of the remaining architectures. Intel Cascade Lake is particularly relevant because such platform is available in AWS coupled with NVIDIA Compute Capability (CC) 7.5 enabled accelerators. Hence, having the Intel Cascade Lake CPU software stack in place immediately enables us to build CC 7.5 compatible applications in AWS cloud instances, which, due to said availability, may be popular for the community at large.

²<https://gitlab.com/eessi/support/-/issues/68>

³<https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/jsc/systems/supercomputers/jureca>

⁴<https://apps.fz-juelich.de/jsc/hps/jureca/evaluation-platform-overview.html#grace-hopper-nodes>

⁵<https://www.macc.fcn.pt/resources>

3 Accelerator targets

In deliverables D1.1 "Report on shared software stack prototype" [1] and D1.3 "Report on stable, shared software stack" [2] we reported on the (initial) support for NVIDIA GPUs. In this section, we will elaborate on the progress and extended support that has been added, and we will outline the current work and plans for adding support for the AMD ROCm ecosystem to EESSI in order to support AMD GPUs as well.

3.1 NVIDIA GPUs

Because software installations are optimized for each system architecture they are built on, a suitable combination of CPU and GPU architecture to build the software is needed. The features available to each NVIDIA GPU are defined as Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) Compute Capability (CC) and depend on the GPU itself and the version of CUDA available on the system. For example, a device that supports CUDA CC 8.0 can use all features up to and including version 8.0. This means it is fully compatible with software built using features from version 7.0 or earlier. At the software level, not all applications can be optimised for more than one CUDA CC, including software that is integral to MultiXscale [2], which makes building the software stack with different combinations of CPU microarchitectures and GPUs all the more important.

We followed a similar approach when choosing which CPU architectures and CUDA Compute Capability combinations to focus on. Our priority is to focus on combinations present in existing and upcoming EuroHPC systems, and covering a wide enough spectrum of CPU and GPU architectures so that most users can find either a matching combination, or a suitable fallback. At the moment, optimized software including key MultiXscale applications are available for combinations such as AMD Zen 2 and Zen 3 CPUs with CUDA CC 8.0, as well as for NVIDIA Grace CPUs with CUDA CC 9.0 (that is, compatible with Grace Hopper systems, which will power the EuroHPC HPC JUPITER).

CPU microarchitecture		CUDA CC			
		7.0	8.0	9.0	
x86_64	generic				
	intel	haswell			
		skylake			
		cascadelake	N		
		icelake		N	
	sapphirerapids				
	amd	zen2		N	
		zen3		N	
zen4				N	
aarch64	generic				
	neoverse_n1				
	neoverse_v1				
	nvidia grace			N	

Table 1: Supported CPU microarchitectures and CUDA CC. An N denotes software builds are done natively on a given CPU-GPU pair (meaning GPU-specific tests are run). All CPU targets can utilize available GPU-enabled software installations.

In Table 1 we show that we are building GPU software for all CPU families for all supported CUDA CCs. However, we only can *test* GPU installations on build nodes that provide a GPU (denoted by N in the Table 1). The subtleties of device code, ptx code and compatibility for NVIDIA GPUs are discussed in detail in [CUDA CC support issue for EESSI](#), and are beyond the scope of the current discussion.

3.2 AMD ROCm support for AMD GPUs

Although AMD datacenter GPUs intended for high-performance computing have been around for several years now, it can still be considered as a somewhat emerging platform in terms of adoption and software supporting this platform. In addition, the AMD ROCm software ecosystem itself is still evolving quite quickly. As an example, broader compatibility guarantees between ROCm software and kernel mode drivers was only introduced with ROCm version 6.4 (released April 11, 2025) [3]. Prior to this, user space software ecosystem updates required administrators to update the GPU drivers (and all software would need to be recompiled!).

Nevertheless, it is a very interesting accelerator architecture to consider next to NVIDIA, also because the EuroHPC LUMI system provides a large number of AMD GPUs. For this reason, we have recently started working on adding support for the ROCm ecosystem to the EESSI software stack.

Most of the work so far has been put into adding support for a more recent ROCm version in EasyBuild. Currently, EasyBuild only supports ROCm version 4.5.0, which was released in 2021. Since then, the ROCm ecosystem and EasyBuild have evolved quite a bit. Thus, we could simply bump the versions of the existing build recipes. Instead, we opted for a new start on building support for recent versions of ROCm in EasyBuild. Additionally, the AMD ROCm software ecosystem is in a comparatively less mature state than NVIDIA's ecosystem [4], which presents additional challenges.

The ROCm compilers are based on an AMD fork of the LLVM compilers, and recently the EasyBuild installation procedures for LLVM compilers were completely overhauled⁶. We have based our work on these new installation procedures for the ROCm LLVM compilers. The interest in having ROCm support built into EasyBuild and EESSI has also been picked up by AMD, and we are currently co-designing the necessary updates to the EasyBuild recipes with the AMD ROCm team⁷.

It is worth mentioning a recent external contribution to EESSI by Inuits in the form of a comprehensive documentation page titled [Overview of ROCm Ecosystem \(v6.4.1-20250526\)](#)⁸, which was accompanied by a [blog post](#)⁹ to highlight the new documentation page. We hope that this additional documentation will help clarify the ROCm ecosystem and serve as a go-to reference for its overall structure and design.

⁶<https://github.com/easybuilders/easybuild-easyblocks/pull/3373>

⁷<https://gitlab.com/eessi/support/-/issues/71>

⁸https://www.eessi.io/docs/site_specific_config/rocm/

⁹<https://www.eessi.io/docs/blog/2025/05/26/rocm/>

4 RISC-V

The RISC-V software stack is being made available via the dedicated CernVM-FS repository `/cvmfs/riscv.eessi.io` (see the [documentation page](#) for details). Much progress has been achieved, with a large number of software applications already available.

4.1 Current status

At the time of writing, the `riscv.eessi.io` repository already contains 468 software packages (about 48% of the packages provided in the production repository for `x86_64` and `aarch64` CPU families) resulting from 468 successful builds. The build procedure used for these builds still required some manual steps, and a lot of effort has been put into aligning the procedures with the ones used for the production software repository `software.eessi.io`: the build scripts of the production repository now support building for RISC-V as well, and a build bot has been set up on a RISC-V cluster at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) to automate software builds and deployments. For the next version of the RISC-V stack, we will start using this new workflow, which is a significant step towards merging the RISC-V stack into the production repository.

Currently, all builds in the RISC-V repository are built for a generic RISC-V processor, i.e. without any microarchitecture-specific optimizations. This was initially chosen because of the lack of RISC-V support in EasyBuild, and it was deemed a more promising approach to get started with building for RISC-V. Also, it makes building and testing easier, as generic builds can be performed and tested on any RISC-V processor, while building for more specialized RISC-V processors would have also required access to a build system where we would could run the build bot.

The experience we have obtained so far, confirmed by the large number of installed applications, is that we ran into relatively few issues when doing these generic builds. For this reason, and since we do have access now to more advanced RISC-V CPUs with RISC-V Vector Extension (RVV), we have started working on adding support for more fine-grained RISC-V CPU detection in EasyBuild, and adding the corresponding build flags for optimized builds. Based on the experiences with ARM CPUs, we may expect more build issues, as the codes using vector instructions are often more prone to build errors and test failures.

An important development that is relevant for the RISC-V software stack is the work done on the support of an LLVM toolchain in EESSI, much of which was the result of external contributions by Davide Grassano (CECAM) to EESSI and EasyBuild alongside the developers of EESSI. The availability of this toolchain will be very useful as it is compatible with a large number of RISC-V CPUs, and likewise, it is a component of the AMD ROCm compilers.

5 Additional improvements

5.1 Installations of additional CPU targets

Providing installations of additional CPU targets creates unique challenges and requires a careful approach, particularly when integrating these into an existing EESSI version. Throughout the life cycle of the first version of the software stack, version 2023.06, five new CPU targets were fully added to the software stack (AMD Zen4, Intel Cascadelake, Intel Icelake, Intel Sapphire Rapids, NVIDIA Grace) and one more is being built (Fujitsu A64FX). Note, we do not list the RISC-V software stack, which is currently being provided via the `riscv.eessi.io` CernVM-FS repository.

The experience we obtained from adding support for these new CPU targets has been very useful in improving the reproducibility of the software stack. Although the EESSI stack is clearly defined using EasyBuild [easystack files](#) and a lot of build information is already stored, we found that some additional build information is required to perform an exact rebuild of an existing stack for a new CPU architecture. Without this information, more manual work is required to obtain the right build order, but ultimately we could complete the builds for these new targets.

For the next version of the EESSI stack, we will store more information for every build (e.g. the build time, full dump of the build configuration) to be able to fully "replay" the build of an existing stack. This should ensure that the stack will be even more reproducible. A first version of scripts that do the rebuild of a stack in this way has already been implemented and has been used for the Intel Cascadelake and Icelake stacks.

Another lesson learned is that achieving full reproducibility may not be completely feasible. Some applications have code deeply hidden in their build scripts that pull in files (or even non-fixed versions of dependencies) on the fly during the build, and a later run of the same scripts may pull in another version. Although this would ideally be controlled by the EasyBuild build recipe, it is sometimes hard to know *a-priori* and thus modify the build recipes accordingly. This only applies to a very small number of builds, though, and in most cases it should not really affect the final installation.

5.2 Development repository

The development of code in MultiXscale use cases requires frequent additions, changes, and tests. Software development in ongoing projects can be fast-paced, which means that distributing development versions under the same conditions as those of the CernVM-FS production repository `software.eessi.io` is not desirable. For this purpose, we created a new CernVM-FS repository – `dev.eessi.io` – that has a few key differences.

- Software can be ingested without being built for all CPU targets;
- Software need not be built from tagged releases, but from any development version obtained from a given commit SHA;
- Software installations are not meant to be permanent, as they are not intended for production use;
- Installations are located in specific project subdirectories in the `dev.eessi.io` CernVM-FS repository;
- It is available as a separate, self-contained instance of the build-test-deploy bot on dedicated (cloud) resources;
- Permissions to trigger builds and deployments can be assigned on a per-project basis, and controlled from project specific GitHub repositories under the MultiXscale (or EESSI) GitHub organisation.

With this approach, a developer for a use case pursued by the MultiXscale CoE can push the most up-to-date development version to their code repository of choice. They can then easily build the application with the most recent changes by adding a few lines on a tailor-made EasyBuild `easystack` file that is stored in a project-specific repository under the [MultiXscale GitHub organization](#). Once the developer opens a pull request with the new changes, a separate instance of the build-test-deploy bot can build the application with those updates. These can then be deployed as soon as the application is built for one (or more) of the desired CPU microarchitectures, while ingestion must still be approved by an EESSI maintainer. From this point on, developers can immediately test their work by accessing any system that mounts the `dev.eessi.io` CernVM-FS repository, including in EuroHPC systems with matching CPU microarchitectures for which the software installations were created. Additionally, it can also then be used as part of CI workflows that test or otherwise use the development build of the application.

The use of project subdirectories, GitHub repositories, and separate bot instances to distribute, control the build procedure, and build the applications ensures that different developer teams can work in parallel without fear of inadvertently disrupting, or even accessing, each other's code and software deployment. This also constitutes a security benefit since each bot instance will only listen to an approved set of GitHub accounts, i.e., those belonging to a given developer team, hence the build environments for each project are accessible only to the authorized user accounts.

6 Conclusion and outlook

EESSI's support for new system architectures has grown substantially, with the software stack now including new CPU microarchitectures and applications built and optimized for CPU-GPU combinations. Our work towards supporting AMD GPUs and ROCm and a wide gamut of NVIDIA GPUs provides researchers with a reliable and optimized software stack regardless of the technologies available on their HPC site. The efforts to expand the number of supported system architectures go beyond the actual software builds, tests, and deployments, but also in refining and expanding existing processes and documentation. These are important steps as they give the HPC community an increasing range of compatible hardware combinations on which the EESSI software stack can provide optimized software that can leverage cutting edge hardware technologies. In addition, we hope that the focus on consistent processes and clear documentation reinforces trust and adoption by users in general, and makes the lives of HPC site administrators easier.

The work towards a mature RISC-V software stack contributes to the budding ecosystem surrounding this emerging architecture, and we hope can aid developers and researchers contribute new RISC-V compatible software.

Lastly, with the development repository we provide MultiXscale CoE developers with a quick and flexible way to build, test, and deploy their software. This can easily be added to existing development workflows, and provide the support and infrastructure for doing so. Our goal is to facilitate development and provide researchers with simple ways to adopt or expand their use of CI, testing, and foster collaboration.

References

Acronyms used

CI	Continuous Integration
CernVM-FS	CernVM File System
EESSI	European Environment for Scientific Software Installations
HPC	High Performance Computing
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
JSC	Jülich Supercomputing Centre
EuroHPC	European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
MACC	Minho Advanced Computing Center
CC	Compute Capability
RVV	RISC-V Vector Extension
JSC	Jülich Supercomputing Centre

Software mentioned

CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture

URLs referenced

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Citations

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